

THE SKILL AND CREATIVITY OF THE EDUCATOR IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF AN INNOVATIVE CLUSTER IN TRAINING

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Annotation: Due to the high social significance of higher education in the sustainable development of society, modern requirements, problems in the system and the prevalence between the branches of Education, Science and production in their solution today necessitate the need to transfer continuing pedagogical education to a cluster development model. The combination of Science and education with production ensures progress in all areas. In this regard, naturally, the integration of Science, Education and production is an important and urgent task. Because, education, science serve as an important factor that determines the future of any society, nation and state, serving its development. In this article, opinions and reflections will be made on the skill and creativity of the educator in the development of an innovative cluster in training.

Keywords: Higher Education, cluster, skill, development, innovative techniques, creativity, practical experience.

Reforms in the field of education in Uzbekistan are carried out directly together with the process of its transition to Democratic, market relations. The idea of preparing young people for a new social environment, educating them in the spirit of the era, reforming the educational sphere, radically improving the system, in particular, introducing the experience of developed foreign countries into the system, is emphasized by the head of our state as one of the urgent and outstanding tasks on the agenda. Therefore, in the concept of the development of the higher education system in the republic until 2030, it is defined as one of the strategic goals and priority directions for the development of the higher education system in order to increase the level of coverage of the population with higher education, to create the necessary conditions for the development of the higher education system

The purpose of teaching is to convey to the student the knowledge and skills set out in the state educational standards. When knowledge is accepted and understood by the reader, or the reader is able to demonstrate in practice the tasks intended for advanced training, it can be assumed that the training was successful. As you know, the process of obtaining education (obtaining information) is a process consisting in the systematic development of spiritual and mental abilities, the formation of knowledge and concepts, and the ability to use the knowledge gained. This process can be carried out through the educator himself or with the support of someone else - the educator. And the learning process takes place based on different techniques(methods).

The educational method is a method of joint activities of teachers and students in the educational process aimed at achieving a specific goal. Educational methods represent ways to achieve the goals set by teaching, as well as ways to orient educational material in theoretical and practical terms. Teaching methods determine what the activities of the teacher and student should be in the educational process, how to organize and conduct the teaching process, and what activities students should perform in this process.

Methods consist of several main groups, each of which, in turn, is divided into subgroups and individual methods that are included in them. According to the organization of educational activities, the transmission, reception, awareness, memorization of educational information, ensuring the application of mastered knowledge in practice, serving the formation of practical skills and abilities, educational methods can be divided into the following groups.

Verbal (methods of receiving educational information through speech and hearing, or verbal techniques - Story, Lecture, conversation, etc.); methods of receiving educational information through visual transmission and vision (visual methods-pictorial, demonstration and other);

Giving educational practice through practical labor actions (practical techniques-exercises, laboratory experiments, labor actions, etc.). In general, the

choice of method is determined by the didactic goals of education and upbringing. However, in different pedagogical situations, the types of activities between the teacher and students change and alternate. Naturally, the methods of training in accordance with these types of activities are closely intertwined.

The choice of methods and methodological techniques in the teacher's preparation for a new topic means balancing their mutual exchange with respect to time and a didactic goal. Ultimately, conditions are created to ensure a high level of mental and practical activity of students. Correctly applied methods will deepen the knowledge of objective reality and increase the scientific and theoretical level of holistic as well as training. Sequentially sorted teaching methods lead to a certain degree of cognitive and professional interest development, activation of independent practical activities. In pedagogy, the criteria for choosing traditional techniques were developed in large quantities, in subsequent years, more than twenty of them are cited in the work of didactic scientists. The criterion for choosing interactive techniques is their high orientation towards the solution of tables for the development of education and training. This criterion is introduced by assessing the possibilities of solving various techniques in one area or another, since their capabilities in mastering the elements of social experience are diverse.

The next criterion for choosing interactive techniques is to correspond to the nature of their educational content. The content of the method is also defined as part of the movement. From this point on, it is clear that this criterion is taken into account. With the help of one method, the content of the topic is fully revealed, while another makes it possible to master it positively.

Another criterion for choosing interactive techniques is their full compliance with the educational capabilities of students, that is, ensuring the unity of their internal and external conditions for effective educational activities.

The use of interactive teaching methods should correspond to the private capabilities of the educator. It is a teaching process with the theory and practice of teaching methods of the pedagogical regularities, with theories of cognition that take

into account the degree of being armed with the theory of the content of education and other existing laws.

In conclusion, the organization provides for the conversion of individual components and the entire cluster. Cluster activity allows you to create a new quality product. The cluster, which is a kind of new approach to education, allows not only to provide the conditions for obtaining education throughout life, but also to re-establish existing and promising connections between the components that ensure the continuity of Education. The cluster operates around important issues related to the integration of existing intellectual resources around current problems of the development of pedagogical education, the establishment of the principle of rational succession in the pedagogical sphere, the preparation of future teachers with practical orientation with quick feedback on the level of satisfaction of interested persons.

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